

INFLUENCE OF COMPOSITE FILTER FABRIC THICKNESS ON AERODYNAMIC RESISTANCE

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Abstract

This study analyzes the effect of the thickness of a filter fabric woven from yarn composed of a combination of glass fiber and Teflon fibers on the aerodynamic characteristics of a bag filter unit. Under dust-free operating conditions, the variation of the overall resistance coefficient, ζ_t , and the aerodynamic resistance, ΔP_t , was investigated for filter fabric thicknesses of $\delta_f = 1.0, 1.5, \text{ and } 2.0$ mm at gas inlet velocities ranging from $v_{in} = 10 \div 20$ m/h. The results indicate that an increase in the filter fabric thickness leads to a corresponding increase in both the overall resistance coefficient and the pressure loss of the unit.

Keywords: filter fabric, glass fiber, polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) fiber, bag filter, aerodynamic resistance, overall resistance coefficient, gas flow velocity, filter thickness.

Introduction.

Bag filter units play a crucial role in the efficient purification of dust-laden gases generated in industrial facilities. The performance of these units largely depends on the physical and mechanical properties of the filter fabric, particularly its thickness, porosity, and capacity to create aerodynamic resistance. In recent years, growing attention has been paid to composite filter materials that combine high thermal resistance, mechanical strength, and chemical stability. In this regard, filter fabrics produced from a combination of glass fibers and PTFE (Teflon) fibers can be considered among the most promising materials.

Glass fibers provide the mechanical framework of the filter material and improve its resistance to elevated temperatures, while PTFE fibers impart surface inertness, reduce dust adhesion, and ensure stable long-term performance. However, the extent to which variations in the thickness of such composite fabrics affect their aerodynamic characteristics still requires further substantiation. Therefore, the present study examines the influence of filter fabric thickness on

the overall resistance coefficient and aerodynamic resistance under dust-free operating conditions.

Main Text.

For this study, the theoretical and experimental values of the overall resistance coefficient, ζ_t , and the aerodynamic resistance, ΔP_t , were compared for a filter fabric woven from yarn composed of a combination of glass fiber and PTFE (Teflon) fibers at three thickness levels, $\delta_f = 1.0, 1.5,$ and 2.0 mm, and within a gas inlet velocity range of $v_{in} = 10 \div 20$ m/s.

The results demonstrated that the overall resistance coefficient increased systematically with increasing filter fabric thickness. For example, at a gas inlet pipe diameter of $D_{in} = 150$ mm and an inlet gas velocity of $v_{in} = 10$ m/s, the theoretical overall resistance coefficient, ζ_t , theor, was 3.58 for the 1 mm-thick fabric, 3.91 for the 1.5 mm-thick fabric, and 4.24 for the 2 mm-thick fabric. The same tendency was preserved at higher velocities. In particular, at $v_{in} = 20$ m/s, the corresponding values were 3.71, 3.86, and 4.32. This behavior can be attributed to the increasing internal resistance to gas flow as the filter layer thickness increases.

A similar relationship was observed for aerodynamic resistance. At $D_{in} = 150$ mm and $v_{in} = 10$ m/s, the theoretical aerodynamic resistance, ΔP_t , theor, amounted to 152.5 Pa for the 1 mm-thick fabric, 165.8 Pa for the 1.5 mm-thick fabric, and 180 Pa for the 2 mm-thick fabric. When the gas velocity was increased to 20 m/s, the corresponding pressure losses reached 630 Pa, 655.8 Pa, and 734.2 Pa, respectively. Therefore, with increasing gas velocity, the aerodynamic resistance rises in a manner close to a quadratic dependence, while greater filter fabric thickness further amplifies this increase.

The discrepancy between the theoretical and experimental values remained within a narrow range, with the error generally varying between 1.7% and 3.75%. This confirms that the selected calculation method and the parameters adopted for the new material are in satisfactory agreement with the experimental results. For example, at $D_{in} = 150$ mm and $v_{in} = 14$ m/s, the theoretical value of ΔP_t for the 1 mm-thick material was 305.8 Pa, while the experimental value was 311 Pa, corresponding to an error of 1.7%. A similarly close agreement was observed for the other thickness values as well.

Based on the obtained results, it can be stated that the thickness of the filter fabric is one of the key structural factors governing aerodynamic resistance. With an increase in thickness, the void channels within the filter medium become reduced, the gas flow path becomes more tortuous, and local flow resistances

increase. Therefore, although thicker materials may ensure higher filtration efficiency, they may be less advantageous from the standpoint of energy consumption and pressure loss.

Discussion.

The obtained results demonstrate that the selection of filter fabric thickness should be based not only on mechanical strength and dust collection capability, but also on the aerodynamic operating regime. While the 1 mm-thick fabric exhibited the lowest resistance to gas flow, the 2 mm-thick fabric produced the highest values of ζ_t and ΔP_t throughout the entire velocity range. This, in turn, increases the fan power requirement during bag filter operation.

The 1.5 mm-thick material represents an intermediate case: it does not lead to a significant increase in aerodynamic resistance, while at the same time ensuring an adequate level of structural stability and filter layer density. Therefore, a thickness of 1.5 mm can be considered a practically justified option. In particular, when energy consumption, pressure loss, and subsequent dust collection efficiency are assessed in combination, this thickness provides performance characteristics close to the optimal operating regime.

Conclusion.

The results of the study showed that the thickness of the filter fabric based on a combination of glass fiber and PTFE (Teflon) fibers has a significant influence on the aerodynamic characteristics of a bag filter unit. As the filter fabric thickness increased from 1 mm to 2 mm, both the overall resistance coefficient, ζ_t , and the aerodynamic resistance, ΔP_t , increased consistently over the entire investigated velocity range. This trend can be attributed to the densification of the filter layer and the corresponding increase in internal resistance to gas flow.

The small discrepancy between the theoretical and experimental results confirmed the reliability of the selected calculation approach. The analysis revealed that the 1 mm-thick fabric was characterized by relatively low aerodynamic resistance, whereas the 2 mm-thick fabric produced the highest pressure loss. At the same time, the 1.5 mm-thick filter fabric can be regarded as a promising option for practical application, as it ensures a relatively favorable balance between aerodynamic resistance and structural stability.

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